

Design and Implementation of Two stage OP-Amp circuit for SAR ADC's

Kotha Lavanya 1^{#1}, Dr.Ajay Kumar Dharmireddy2^{#2}.

#1 Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering,
9490607600. and Sir C.R.Reddy College of Engineering, Eluru-534007 India.

#2 Associate Professor, Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
Sir C.R.Reddy College of Engineering, 7989379619, and ajaybabuji@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

In this work, an operational amplifier (Op-Amp) is the key component in the construction of analogue and digital designs. This study described the design and implementation of the Op-Amp circuit is used in many places in the design of SAR ADC architecture. Low power and high-resolution Successive approximate Register (SAR) type ADCs are very much required in the AI-IOT portable applications. The proposed two-stage operational amplifier is designed with 0.18 μ m CMOS technology with a phase margin of 70dB, operating voltage at 1.8v, <300 μ W power consumption and gain has > 90 dB. Obtained bias current as 10 μ A. Gain 60.36 dB and UGB 20.59 and Power dissipation 616.31 microwatts. >90dB consuming a power <300 μ W..

Keywords: Operational Amplifier, Low Power, High speed, CMOS technology, Analog to Digital Converter.

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Corresponding Author: Ajaykumar Dharmireddy

INTRODUCTION

Operational amplifiers (op-amps) are crucial for the Successive Approximation Register (SAR) Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) to function properly [1]. Op-amps are used by the SAR ADC at several stages to speed up signal processing and guarantee precise Analog-to-digital conversion. The functions of operational amplifiers in a SAR ADC are described below. Converting digital codes into equivalent currents is one of the crucial phases in a SAR ADC [2]. These digital codes are transformed into currents by op-amps using a technique known as voltage-to-current conversion. The op-amp transforms the binary digital code into proportional currents based on the bit weights in conjunction with a resistor ladder network [3]. The ladder network's resistors are arranged according to the weight of each bit, and the op-amp transforms the binary bits into the corresponding current levels.

Operational amplifiers are crucial in the DAC stage of a SAR ADC due to their adaptability and capacity for a variety of signal processing tasks. They make it possible for digital codes to be converted into currents, which are then added together to produce an Analog voltage, interface with comparators for comparison, offer feedback control, and maybe boost the output voltage [8]. These tasks are essential to a SAR ADC's accurate operation and help to achieve high-resolution and accurate Analog-to-digital conversion.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of op-amp circuit.

A versatile electrical component called an operational amplifier (op-amp) amplifies the voltage difference between two input terminals. It serves as a fundamental building component in the construction of mixed-signal and Analog circuits [9]. Here is an explanation of a typical operational amplifier in a block diagram. The inverting input (-) and the non-inverting input (+) are the op-amp's two input terminals. Where the input voltage is located is the inverting input (-), which is typically denoted by a negative sign. Another input voltage or a reference voltage can be applied to the non-inverting input (+). The differential amplifier at the heart of an op-amp increases the voltage difference between inputs that are inverting and those that are not. This differential amplifier's gain is extremely high, frequently in the tens of thousands or higher [10]. The gain stage receives the differential amplifier's output after that. The gain step further increases the differential voltage's amplitude. Depending on the op-amp arrangement and other

components, the gain can be adjusted. The gain stage's enhanced output is subsequently routed through an output stage. The output stage offers the required voltage compliance and current drive to deliver the amplified output signal [11]. This is the input signals that have been amplified and processed, usually with reference to a ground potential. Power supply pins on the op-amp furnish it with the energy it needs to function. The op-amp block diagram highlights its capacity to amplify the voltage difference between the two input terminals with a high gain while also illustrating its fundamental construction and functionality.

LITERATURE SURVAY

Taherzadeh, Mohammad, & et al [12], 2014 described 0.18 μ m CMOS technology. Designed and fabricated a 10-bit SARADC with 110-kS/s sample rate for biomedical applications resulted with 56.1dB of SNDR, 67dB of SFDR, FOM of 20fJ, power consumption of 1.16 μ W operating at from 1.5V Analog, and 1.2V digital power supplies with a sinusoidal input of 39.5 kHz. Wherein INL amidst range -1.23 LSB and 1.19 LSB, and the DNL range -0.71 LSB and 0.92 LSB. 0.18 μ m CMOS technology, designed a two stage Op-Amp with phase margin of 70.6 dB, operating at 1.8v, power consumption as 616.31micro Watts. and offset voltage of 16.91micro volts. Obtained bias current as 10 μ A. Gain 60.36 dB and UGB 20.59 and Power dissipation 616.31 micro watt

Richter, Tzschoppe, et.[13], 0.18 μ m CMOS technology, designed a fully differential operational amplifier with gain bandwidth of 2.03 GHz and phase margin is 55degrees, power consumption is 2.25mwatts. Operating at 1.8volts.60.8 dB open loop gain is obtained.

Rathore & Darji et al.[14], described as 0.18 μ m CMOS technology, designed a cascade operational amplifier targeted for high speed, high bandwidth applications here main contribution in this paper is this design is operating at 3.3v obtained gain is 39.5db and phase margin is 56.8 degrees. UGB is 539.3 Mhz. and CMRR is 57.79db and slew rate is 365uV/S.

Mai & Weigel et al.[15],0.18 μ m CMOS technology designed a Op-Amp which works like a differential amplifier with a slew rate as 70V/us and on delay of 205ns and off delay of 30ns. Operating at 5v power supply it is a fully differential Op-Amp for common mode feedback circuit for a fast startup technique, with obtained UGB is 20 MHz and slew rate is 70v/us.

Rajput & Hemant et al.[16], presents 0.35 μ m CMOS process based two stage Op-Amp design produces an open loop gain of 78dB and improved gain bandwidth GBW is of 5.82MHz. with a PM 63.9 degrees. Operates at 3.3V and has a power dissipation of 144.3 uW. and with offset voltage of 61.5uV. Power consumption of 144uW. In this process obtained parameters are 81db gain 5 MHz UGB Phase margin is 65 degrees, slew rate as 6.5V/us Power dissipation is 378 micro watts. CMOS BIO Amplifier by using a twostage opamp with 250nm, 90nm technology. Operates with +/- 2.5V and +/-1.2 V supply respectively. Carries a 5.56mw, 15.53 μ w respectively, have an open loop gain of 82 dB and the CMRR of 92 dB, operates at \pm 1.2v and open loop gain of 72.9 dB, CMRR of 73.03 dB

EXITING MODEL

Fig. 2. Existing model Op-Amp circuit diagram

Fig.2 is the basic Op-Amp, where the transistors M_1 , M_2 , M_3 and M_4 form differential amplifier, M_6 , and M_7 transistors made second stage of gain amplifier, and transistor M_8 , and M_5 employed a current mirror circuit [2]. Op-Amp design parameters are gain, bandwidth, linearity, noise, and output swings.

Design equations of Existing Model

Op-Amp structure involves the selection of transistors and their interconnections in the circuit. This circuit can not change until and unless it is not able to meet the design specifications. Selection of transistors sizes and dc currents involves the transistor sizes can be modified by adjusting W/L ratios, and the dc currents also required to be modified.

Initially the compensating capacitor C_C is calculated, Where C_L load capacitance. For 60 degrees phase we consider RHP Zero at or beyond 10 times Gain Bandwidth and second pole P2 is placed 2.2times higher than the GB resulting

$$C_C > \left(\frac{2.2}{10}\right) C_L \quad (1)$$

Hence, we can derive the minimum capacitance Using the slew rate and compensation capacitance we now find the Bias current i.e., Tail current (I_5).

$$I_5 = SR * C_C \quad (2)$$

Requirement of trans-conductance of the input Transistors is calculated from C_C and Gain Bandwidth.

$$g_{m1} = GB * C_c * 2\pi \quad (3)$$

The aspect ratio of differential transistors can be obtained as below

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_{1\&2} = \frac{g_m^2}{\mu_n C_{ox} 2I_D} \quad (4)$$

Calculating aspect ratio of load transistors using ICMR requirements,

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_{3\&4} = \frac{2I_D}{\mu_p C_{ox} (V_{DD} - ICMR_{MAX} - |V_{THP}| + V_{THN})^2} \quad (5)$$

For Keeping Tail current Transistor in saturation calculated V_{DSAT} .

$$V_{DSAT} \geq ICMR - \sqrt{\frac{2I_{D1}}{\beta}} - V_{THMAX} \quad (6)$$

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_5 = \frac{2I_D}{\mu_n C_{ox} (V_{DSAT})^2}; \quad \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_5 = \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_8$$

Assumed $gm_6 = 10gm_1$

Calculating $gm_4 = \sqrt{\mu_n C_{ox} X \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_4 X 2I_D}$

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_6 = \left(\frac{gm_6}{gm_4}\right) \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_4$$

Calculating current Through gain stage

$$I_6 = \frac{gm^2}{2\mu_p C_{ox} X \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_6} \quad (7)$$

Finally Calculated aspect ratio of

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_7 = \left(\frac{I_6}{I_5}\right) * \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_5$$

Current Bias circuit for desired is designed using the equation

$$= \frac{2}{2\mu_n C_{ox} X \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_n} X \frac{1}{R_S^2} X \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{K}}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

Calculation of gain $A_D = gm_1 gm_2 r_{d6} r_{d7}$

where $gm_2 = gm_6 || gm_7$

Table 1: Design parameters and values of Existing model

S.No	Deign parameters	Values
1	Technology	180nm
2	Supply	3.3V
3	Gain	>90dB
4	Phase Margin	>60°
5	UGB	>5MHz
6	Slew rate	> 10V/ μs
7	Power Dissipation	<300μW

The basic Op-Amp is designed to the given specifications, and then simulated. Table 1 shows the tabulated values of both calculated and simulated and comparison.

PROPOSED MODEL

As the gain of basic Op-Amp is very low, hence, cascoding configuration is employed to the basic circuit to improve the gain in the second stage as shown in figure 2, and the modified Op-Amp

circuit is shown in Fig. 3. The transistors M₉ and M₁₀ forms cascoding with M₆ and M₇ transistors, and their gain directly affected by their trans-conductance terms. To compensate for the lower gain that comes from opting for the higher slew rate and larger UGB. To make the design more robust, the differential mode gain has been adjusted according to the provided equation, which involves the addition of a zero under the precise control of circuit component resistor R.

Fig. 3 Proposed Model of modified Op-Amp circuit

Design equations of Existing Model

Initially the compensating capacitor CC is calculated where CL load capacitance.

For 60° Phase we consider RHP zero at or beyond 10 times GB (Gain bandwidth) and second pole P2 is placed 2.2times higher than GB resulting

$$C_L > \left(\frac{2.2}{10}\right) C_L \quad (8)$$

Hence, we can derive the minimum capacitance, Using the slew rate and compensation capacitance we now find the Bias current i.e., Tail current I_S

$$I_S = SR * C_C \quad (9)$$

Requirement of trans-conductance of the input Transistors is calculated from CL and GB is $g_{m1} = GB * C_c * 2\pi$

The aspect ratio of differential transistors can be obtained as below.

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_{1\&2} = \frac{g_{m1}^2}{\mu_n C_{ox} 2I_D} \quad (10)$$

Calculating aspect ratio of load transistors using ICMR requirements,

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_{3\&4} = \frac{2I_D}{\mu_p C_{ox} (V_{DD} - ICMR_{MAX} - |V_{THP}| + V_{THN})^2}$$

For keeping tail current Transistor in saturation calculated V_{DSAT}

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_{3\&4} = \frac{2I_D}{\mu_P C_{ox} (V_{DD} - ICMR_{MAX} - |V_{THP} + V_{THN}|)^2}$$

For Keeping Tail current Transistor in saturation calculated V_{DSAT}

$$V_{DSAT} \geq ICMR - \sqrt{\frac{2I_{D1}}{\beta}} - V_{THMAX} \tag{11}$$

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_5 = \frac{2I_D}{\mu_n C_{ox} (V_{DSAT})^2} \tag{12}$$

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_5 = \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_8$$

Assumed $g_{m6} = 10g_{m1}$

Calculating $g_{m4} = \sqrt{\mu_P C_{ox} \times \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_4 \times 2I_D}$

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_6 = \left(\frac{g_{m6}}{g_{m4}}\right) \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_4$$

$$\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_9 = \left(\frac{g_{m9}}{g_{m4}}\right) \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_4$$

Calculated Current Through gain stage

$$I_6 = \frac{g_m^2}{2\mu_P C_{OX} \times \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_6} \tag{13}$$

$$I_9 = \frac{g_m^2}{2\mu_P C_{OX} \times \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_9} \tag{14}$$

Finally Calculated aspect ratio of $\left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_7 = \left(\frac{I_6}{I_5}\right) * \left(\frac{W}{L}\right)_5$

Table 2: Design parameters and values of proposed model

S.No	Deign parameters	Values
1	Technology	180nm
2	Supply	<3.3V
3	Gain	>90dB
4	Phase Margin	>60°
5	UGB	>5MHz
6	Slew rate	> 10V/ μs
7	Power Dissipation	<300μW

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fix the voltages $V_{DC}=V_{DD}=3.3V(+1.65V \ \& \ -1.65V)$, apply an AC signal $V_{ac}= A \sin \omega t$ with magnitude=1V and amplitude=500mV, set the common mode voltage as 500mV, bias voltage to 404mV and bias current I_{DC} to 50uA.

Fig. 4 Gain plot of Proposed Model Op-Amp circuit

Two differential sinusoid signals with the frequency from 10kHz to 10MHz along with load capacitors of 200fF connect to two inputs. The operating voltage is 3.3V and 0.18 μm SCL process technology.

The figure 4 shows the gain plot of an operational amplifier plotted and obtained gain is 96.5dB

Fig. 5 Phase plot of Proposed Model Op-Amp circuit

The figure 5 shows the phase plot of an operational amplifier is 77° . Op-Amp simulation results i.e., gain and phase bode plots are presented in figure 4 and figure 5 respectively. From these plots gain margin, phase margin, bandwidth, and unity gain frequency (UGF) are measured and shown in the comparison table. From the gain plot, obtained the $GM=96.5\text{dB}$ and from the phase plot, the obtained $PM=77^\circ$

Gain of proposed model Op-Amp:

Gain of the basic operational amplifier is given by the equation $A_D=g_{m1}g_{m2}r_{d6}r_{d7}$

Where $g_{m2}=g_{m6}\parallel g_{m7}$

Gain of Proposed model modified Op-Amp:

Gain of the proposed amplifier is given by the equation $A_D=G_m r_{d6} r_{d7} r_{d9} r_{d10}$

Where $G_m=g_{m1}g_{m2}$ and $g_{m2}=(g_{m6}+g_{m9})\parallel(g_{m7}+g_{m10})$

Table 3 Comparison of designed work with existing models

parameter	Proposed design	Existing design	Ref [10]	Ref [11]
Technology, μm	0.18	0.18	0.13	0.5
Supply voltage, V	3.3V	3.3	0.25	3.3
DC Gain, dB	96.50	73	60	82
Phase Margin, deg	77	62	53	83
Power Dissipation, mW	0.168	0.135	0.18	1.2
Slew rate, $\text{v}/\mu\text{s}$	8.463	7.9	0.0007	10
UGBW, MHz	12.378	4.12	0.002	12
Load capacitance, pF	2	2	15	30

The proposed Op-Amp parameters are extracted through both analytical approach and simulations are presented in table 5. Gain margin of the proposed Op-Amp is improved to 96 dB from 73 dB.

CONCLUSION

Op-Amp is operating with the frequency up to 12 MHz, $PM=77^\circ$, $GM=96.50\text{dB}$ which is nearing to 100dB, and the power consumption of this design is $168\mu\text{W}$. This Op-Amp is used in high speed and low power applications in SAR ADC circuits

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